

Synchronization of a Perturbed Satellite Attitude Motion

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Abstract : In this paper, the predictive control method is proposed to control the synchronization of two perturbed satellites attitude motion. Based on delayed feedback control of continuous-time systems combines with the prediction-based method of discrete-time systems, this approach only needs a single controller to realize synchronization, which has considerable significance in reducing the cost and complexity for controller implementation.

Keywords : predictive control, synchronization, satellite attitude, control engineering

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